

TAX DESIGN MATTERS: THE IMPACT OF CIGARETTE EXCISE TAX STRUCTURE IN SHAPING GOVERNMENT REVENUES IN THE EU

*Kornienko N.
Ph.D.,*

Independent researcher

Abstract

The ongoing reform of the EU Tobacco Tax Directive creates an important opportunity to reassess how tobacco taxation can serve government fiscal objectives, particularly in raising stable and predictable revenues. This paper examines how different excise tax designs influence government revenue collection across EU member states, with a focus on the revenue effects of relying on specific versus ad valorem components.

The analysis employs a fixed-effects panel regression covering 27 EU countries from 2010 to 2024. In the analysis two hypotheses are tested: first, whether systems with a high reliance on specific excise taxation generate higher per capita tobacco tax revenues; and second, whether the revenue impact of such systems depends on regular adjustments to the specific tax component, such as indexation.

The results show that countries with a high share of specific excise taxes consistently collect more tobacco tax revenue per capita than those relying more on ad valorem taxation. The regression results suggest that the EU could potentially collect an additional €4 billion in revenue. However, this estimate should be interpreted with caution, as other unobserved factors may influence revenue outcomes. This increase is associated with a higher reliance on the specific component within the overall tax structure, even without raising tax rates, although other factors may also contribute. However, the analysis also reveals that, in the absence of indexation, increases in the specific share are associated with declines in revenue, likely reflecting erosion in real tax levels over time. By contrast, when specific taxes are regularly indexed, each additional percentage point in the specific share is associated with a positive and statistically significant change in revenue.

Based on this evidence, two key policy recommendations emerge:

1. EU member states may wish to consider prioritising specific excise taxes over ad valorem components to enhance fiscal returns, while considering national circumstances and administrative capacity.
2. Specific tax systems should incorporate adjustment mechanisms to safeguard revenues against inflation and market shifts.

Keywords: Excise tax, government revenues, tobacco, specific tax component, tax policy, tax collections, indexation, stable fiscal outcomes.

1. Introduction

The structure of a country's tax system is widely recognized as a key determinant of government revenue performance and long-term sustainability (Hines and Summers, 2009; Bucovetsky and Wilson, 1991). Globally, governments are confronted with the challenge of designing tax frameworks that not only ensure adequate revenue generation but also foster economic efficiency, equity, and, where applicable, support public health objectives. The composition of tax instruments, such as the relative shares of corporate tax, VAT, and excise tax, has significant implications for government revenue. Within a tax instrument, the structure (i.e., the balance between specific and ad valorem components) also affects both the level and volatility of revenues.

The design of an excise tax system for tobacco products should aim to balance fiscal and health objectives: ensuring adequate revenues while reducing tobacco consumption and related health risks. In the EU, excise taxation serves as a key instrument of both fiscal and public health policy.

Over the past decades, the EU has engaged in an active debate on the merits of shifting towards a fully specific excise system. Both theoretical and empirical evidence suggest that specific taxation delivers more predictable fiscal revenues, reduces opportunities for tax avoidance by manufacturers, and strengthens market transparency. At the same time, its effectiveness de-

pends heavily on robust administration and enforcement. Without strict tax discipline, the shift toward specific taxation may increase incentives for illicit trade and undermine the revenue base. This raises an important policy question: can the adoption of a fully specific excise, combined with effective enforcement, deliver sustainable positive outcomes for EU Member States, both in terms of fiscal revenues and public health gains?

Theoretical and empirical work converge on this point. Keen (1998) and subsequent studies show that only under strict enforcement and effective administration can specific excises deliver their intended potential, reducing opportunities for tax evasion and securing both higher fiscal revenues and lower consumption. Recent empirical evidence reinforces this conclusion. Primorac et al. (2024) find that while both tax types contribute to revenue, specific excise taxes yield more stable and predictable fiscal streams, largely by limiting consumer down-trading to cheaper brands. By contrast, ad valorem taxes remain more vulnerable to market price shifts and consumer substitution. These findings are directly relevant for policymakers seeking to balance fiscal stability with broader societal goals, including the reduction of harmful consumption.

Despite a longstanding debate in the public finance literature regarding optimal tax structure, empirical evidence on the direct relation between tax structure and government revenue remains limited. Accordingly, this study seeks to contribute to the literature by

examining the effects of different excise tax types, most notably specific and ad valorem excise taxes, on government revenues across the EU.

This paper presents a panel data analysis comparing the revenue performance of specific versus ad valorem tobacco excise tax structures across 27 EU countries over a 15-year period.

While previous literature has proposed theoretical arguments and presented case-specific observations, this study provides systematic, cross-national evidence to analyse the revenue performance of specific taxation, especially when combined with indexation. The study employs a fixed-effects regression framework to control for unobserved heterogeneity across countries and years. While this approach improves internal validity, it may not fully eliminate the possibility that observed revenue effects are influenced by other country-specific or temporal factors. By employing a fixed-effects panel regression and controlling for key confounding factors, we demonstrate that a higher reliance on specific excise taxes, particularly when regularly indexed to inflation, is associated with stronger and more stable per capita tobacco tax revenues. Our findings quantify the potential fiscal gains from excise tax reform and offer nuanced policy guidance, filling a gap in the literature by moving beyond theoretical arguments and case studies to robust, large-scale evidence.

It is important to note that the economic effects discussed throughout this analysis are specific to the European customs union. The customs union framework significantly influences both the regulatory environment and market responses in EU member states, setting them apart from countries outside such unions. In contrast, countries that have implemented significant tobacco tax reforms, such as Australia, New Zealand, and Canada, are not members of a comparable customs union. As a result, their tax structures are not subject to harmonized excise directives or common external tariffs, giving them greater flexibility to design fiscal policies tailored to their specific needs.

2. Literature Review

Academic literature has extensively examined the impact of excise tax structures on consumer behaviour, particularly in the context of cigarette taxation. The growing body of literature highlights the role of tax design in shaping consumption patterns, supporting public health objectives, and enhancing revenue generation amid global fiscal tightening. Empirical evidence underscores the effectiveness of well-designed excise taxes in promoting price increases, revenue stability, and health outcomes.

The question of shifting from a mixed excise structure to a uniform specific excise is a particular case of the broader problem of optimal taxation, originally formulated by Ramsey in the early twentieth century. His framework sought to minimize deadweight losses from taxation while preserving revenues and has since been applied to evaluate the relative merits of specific and ad valorem excises. The analysis becomes more complex under conditions of imperfect competition. In such settings, the tobacco sector can be modelled in different ways: as an oligopoly when the emphasis is on government regulation, as monopolistic competition

when consumer preferences are central, or as a differentiated-product oligopoly when the focus is on competitive dynamics.

The EU tobacco sector is highly concentrated. Therefore, early theoretical contributions treated the EU tobacco sector as an oligopolistic industry. Delipalla and Keen (1992) argued that under imperfect competition ad valorem taxation could lower prices and profits while enhancing overall welfare. Similarly, Myles (1996) found that a mix of both instruments could maximize revenues, with the ad valorem component reducing firms' market power and bringing outcomes closer to perfect competition. Taken together, these early models suggested that raising the ad valorem share while minimizing the specific component might align with fiscal and health objectives. However, such analyses did not account for the role of illicit trade, a critical omission in later debates.

Subsequent research incorporated the role of the illegal tobacco market and found that ad valorem increases provide stronger incentives for illicit trade than specific increases. Delipalla (2009), in examining tax harmonization in the EU, demonstrated three core results clarifying how tax systems need to be adjusted to reduce the market share of illicit products. Crucially, shifting the balance toward specific taxation reduces incentives for illegal trade while safeguarding fiscal revenues.

Other studies have shown that under conditions of cost uncertainty (for instance, input price volatility), ad valorem excises amplify fluctuations in output and prices, whereas specific taxes deliver greater predictability in revenue collection (Kotsogiannis and Serfes 2013). Goerke (2008, 2011) and Delipalla and O'Donnell (1998) further demonstrated that, under imperfect competition, specific excises are more effective in limiting the affordability of cheap cigarettes, thereby raising retail prices, and reducing consumption, an outcome of central importance for public health.

These findings are aligned with the WHO FCTC and the broader economic literature, including Laffer (2014). Article 6 and the related guidelines of the FCTC emphasize that excise structures should minimize incentives for consumers to shift to cheaper brands or categories in response to tax-induced price changes. A uniform specific tax does not fully eliminate opportunities for down-trading but ensures that any switch to cheaper products does not erode tax revenues, since the same amount of tax is levied per unit regardless of price. Laffer similarly underscores that the main advantages of a uniform specific tax are its ability to reduce substitution toward cheaper products, preserve the tax base, and secure revenue independent of firms' pricing strategies. Taken together, the evidence highlights that finding the optimal balance between ad valorem and specific excises remains a complex policy challenge, given the dual objectives of improving public health and containing illicit trade.

More recent studies, such as Primorac and Jeric (2017), confirm that higher specific taxation leads to a statistically significant reduction in cigarette consumption, whereas ad valorem increases do not. Moreover, specific tax increases raise excise revenues, while ad valorem rates have no significant effect. In practice, ad

valorem components are increasingly used to protect domestic producers rather than to achieve fiscal or health objectives. A study conducted by Primorac et al. (2024) analyses the effects of excise tax structures on cigarette pricing across EU member states, with particular emphasis on the pass-through rate of ad-valorem and specific taxes to consumers. Similarly, Chaloupka et al. (2010) provides an extensive analysis across 21 EU member states between 1998 and 2007, showing that reliance on ad-valorem taxes widens price gaps and increases volatility of revenues.

International financial institutions such as the IMF and the World Bank have increasingly engaged in tobacco taxation reform as part of broader efforts to strengthen public health systems and enhance domestic revenue mobilization. Tobacco taxes are viewed with a dual objective: reducing the health burden and external costs associated with smoking, while generating sustainable revenue. Within this context, international financial institutions' recommendations emphasize three core principles: (i) the greater effectiveness of specific excise taxes compared to ad valorem taxes, (ii) the simplification of tax regimes through a reduction in tiers, and (iii) the adoption of gradual, incremental increases through long-term planning or inflation-adjusted indexation. These principles are supported by empirical and policy evidence. Specific taxes are preferred over ad valorem taxes due to their greater effectiveness in reducing consumption and generating stable, predictable revenues. They also reduce incentives for consumers to substitute higher-priced brands for lower-priced ones, a behaviour especially relevant for poorer and younger smokers given budget constraints (WHO, 2010). Simplification of tax structures improves administrative efficiency and limits opportunities for avoidance, while

inflation-adjusted increases preserve the real value of specific taxes. Collectively, these guidelines reinforce the rationale for specific-heavy systems as both fiscally robust and aligned with public health objectives.

3. Institutional Context and European Experience

3.1. Excise tax structure

The design of tobacco excise taxation varies substantially across countries, reflecting differing policy objectives and institutional legacies. Broadly, three approaches to tobacco taxation can be identified in the global landscape. Some countries employ a purely specific excise system, where taxes are levied as a fixed amount per unit (e.g., Indonesia). Others utilize a purely ad valorem system, taxing tobacco as a proportion of its value (e.g., Saudi Arabia). A third group adopts a mixed system, combining both specific and ad valorem components; this approach is employed in EU countries.

The relative importance of each component in mixed systems is not uniform. For instance, Denmark applies a high specific excise rate and a nominal 1% ad valorem rate on cigarettes, resulting in the specific component accounting for most of the tax revenue. Figure 1 presents a global overview, classifying countries by predominant source of cigarette excise tax revenue. For countries with a mixed system, classification is based on the share of each tax type in the weighted average price (WAP) of cigarettes; the larger share determines the country's allocation. In the figure, grey denotes a greater reliance on specific excises, while dashed colour indicates predominance of ad valorem taxes. In this sample, most countries derive the majority of cigarette tax revenue from specific excises, whereas European countries exhibit considerable heterogeneity.

Figure 1

Map indicating the predominant source of cigarette tax revenue: specific excise (grey) vs. ad valorem (dashed)
Notes: This figure illustrates countries with greater reliance on specific taxes (grey) vs. ad valorem taxes for excise taxes of cigarettes.

The evolution of the specific excise share in total tobacco excise taxation within the EU has been similarly diverse. Figure 2 depicts shares of specific or ad valorem tax components within EU member states on

overall excises on cigarettes, ranging from a specific share as low as 14.0% in Luxembourg, to an almost fully specific tax system of 98.5% in Denmark.

Figure 2: Structure of the excise taxes on cigarettes in EU countries in 2025

Notes: Source: [European Commission \(2025\)](#)

Tobacco excises in the EU countries are regulated by the provisions of the Directive on excise duties for manufactured tobacco (Council Directive 2011/64/EU), which mandates that cigarettes be subject to a mixed excise tax structure including a specific component of expressed as a fixed amount per 1,000 cigarettes, and an ad valorem component - expressed as a percentage of the maximum retail selling price.

3.2. Illicit trade

Illicit cigarette trade in the EU is highly responsive to changes in excise tax rates and enforcement. Rapid tax increases often coincide with surges in illicit activity, especially in border regions and where price gaps are large. The shadow market is supply-driven, with intermediaries sourcing products through legal, counterfeit, and smuggling channels. Like legal trade, illicit transactions are shaped by affordability and demand elasticity, but benefit from evading taxes and regulatory measures, operating under more favourable financial conditions. World Bank (2017) estimates suggest illicit trade lowers average retail prices by about 4% and raises overall consumption by 2%, though these figures do not reveal the true market size due to displacement and risk premium uncertainties.

International evidence (WHO, WCO, IMF, World Bank, ITIC) shows that legitimate products are often used to mask illicit flows, making exclusive reliance on

unregulated sources rare. The effectiveness of enforcement and control mechanisms is therefore crucial. According to the IMF (2016), illegal trade occurs via smuggling, counterfeit stamps, and illicit production, causing revenue losses and undermining tax policy and public health. Addressing this requires comprehensive strategies: stronger border controls, modern detection technologies, capacity-building, and international co-operation.

A key element is robust tracking and tracing systems, with unique identifiers enabling authorities to monitor products from manufacture to sale. The EU has advanced such systems, aligning with international standards, and ensuring independence from the tobacco industry (World Bank, 2019).

Despite a long-term decline in aggregate cigarette consumption (from 660 billion units in 2007 to 424 billion in 2024), illicit and non-domestic legal consumption remain significant, 9.2% and 6.2% of total consumption, respectively, in 2024 (see Figures 3 and 4). Illicit consumption fell from 9.8% to 7.2% between 2010 and 2019, then rose again post-pandemic. Increases in ad valorem taxes tend to widen price gaps and incentivise illicit trade, while specific taxes compress price differentials and reduce illicit profit margins. Regular indexation of specific rates, combined with strong enforcement, is essential for improving public health and revenue outcomes across the EU.

Figure 3: Total manufactured cigarette consumption in EU27 Countries from 2007 to 2024 (bn. cigarettes).

Source: KPMG (2013-2025). *Illicit Cigarette Consumption in Europe*.

Note: Legal non-domestic refers to a product that is brought into the market legally by consumers, such as during cross-border trip.

Figure 4: Average excise tax yield per 1,000 cigarettes and illicit cigarette consumption in EU27 Countries from 2015 to 2025.

Source: KPMG (2013-2025). Illicit Cigarette Consumption in Europe, European Commission (2015, 2025).

3.3. Country-Level Illustrations: Austria and the Czech Republic

This subsection examines two country cases. Austria represents a case of increasing reliance on specific taxes alongside rising revenues, while the Czech Republic illustrates the opposite trajectory.

Austria has traditionally implemented a higher proportion of ad valorem than specific excise taxes. However, in recent years the government introduced gradual changes to the cigarette excise structure, which have seen the importance of specific excise taxes grow considerably. While, in 2023, the specific excise proportion of total taxation in Austria of 36.1% remained

below the EU average of 44.5%, the changes in the burden of specific and ad valorem excise taxes are due to rebalancing undertaken by the Austrian authorities.

The specific excise tax rate rose from EUR 26.69 per 1,000 cigarettes in 2010 to EUR 83.5 in 2025. During the same period, the ad valorem rate as a percentage of the retail selling price (RSP) declined from 43.0% to 32%. As a result, the share of the specific component in total taxation increased from 18.28% in 2010 to 36.3% in 2025. Over the same period, tax receipts from cigarettes in Austria increased from EUR 1.5 billion in 2010 to EUR 2.1 billion in 2024 (see Figure 5). This increase reflects the joint effect of rising specific rates and retail prices, consistent with the revenue-enhancing pattern observed in high-specificity regimes.

Figure 5: Tobacco excise tax revenues and proportion of specific excise as a percentage of total taxation in Austria 2010 to 2024.

Source: European Commission (2025) Excise duty tables on tobacco.

In contrast, the Czech Republic has historically placed a higher weight on the specific component of cigarette taxation. The specific excise tax rate rose from EUR 42.09 per 1,000 cigarettes in 2010 to EUR 90.2 in 2025. During the same period, the ad valorem rate as a percentage of RSP rose from 28.0% to 30.0%. However, the specific share declined from 42.5% in 2021 to 39.9% in 2023. During this same period, total tobacco

excise revenue fell from CZK 59 billion to CZK 52 billion (see Figure 6). This reversal aligns with the regression findings presented earlier: a weakening of the specific component, absent compensating adjustments, is associated with declining revenue performance.

Taken together, the experiences of Austria and the Czech Republic illustrate the broader pattern emerging from the panel analysis. Strengthening the specific

share, especially when combined with regular adjustment mechanisms can contribute to higher and more stable government revenue from tobacco taxation. Conversely, erosion of the specific share may undermine

revenue outcomes even in systems that initially relied heavily on specific taxes.

Figure 6: Tobacco excise tax revenues and proportion of specific excise as a percentage of total taxation in the Czech Republic 2010 to 2023.

Source: European Commission (2025) Excise duty tables on tobacco.

4. Methodology

To complete the initial observations about the positive correlation between tobacco excise tax revenue and the proportion of specific excise taxes to total taxation in Austria and the Czech Republic, we turn towards regression analysis.

This section describes the identification strategy to estimate the impact of cigarette excise tax structure on government revenues. By analysing the evolution of excise tax revenues in EU countries over time, it aims to identify whether excise tax structure has a significant impact on governments' ability to raise revenues, considering market size, prices, and tax levels, and controlling for other differences between countries that may affect revenue levels and evolution over time.

Using EU countries allows to build a panel of complete and comparable market data for 27 countries

over 10 years, including tax revenues, sales volumes, prices, and excise tax structure.

4.1. Variables

The variable of interest is the revenue from cigarette excise taxes. To make cigarette excise tax revenues comparable across countries of different size, we calculate cigarette tax revenues per capita by dividing total annual cigarette tax revenues with the population size of the respective year. The resulting annual tax revenues per capita are used as the dependent variable.

Regarding independent variables we are mostly interested in ad valorem and specific tax rates. However, as we are not interested in the effect of the level of taxes, but the composition of taxes on tax revenues, we transform the specific tax rates to a specific ratio. The specific ratio is the share of the specific component on the total excise tax at the weighted average price (WAP):

$$\text{specific ratio} = \frac{\text{specific tax rate}}{\text{total excise tax at WAP}} = \frac{\text{specific tax rate}}{\text{specific tax rate} + \text{ad valorem tax rate} * \text{WAP}}$$

To capture the other factors that may affect the tax revenues as well as the tax structure, we additionally add the share of the illicit market and inflation to the regression as control variables.

4.2. Specification

We estimate two specifications in a two-way fixed-effects framework (country- and year-fixed effects), controlling for inflation and the illicit market share. The dependent variable, Rev_{it} , is government cigarette excise tax revenue per capita in country i in year t . Our policy variable is the specific ratio S_{it} . Specification 1 tests for a threshold (high-specific) regime using a dummy variable $D_{it}^{high} = 1[SR_{it} \geq 0.70]$.

$$Rev_{it} = \beta_1 D_{it}^{high} + \delta^T X_{it} + \mu_i + \tau_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

$$Rev_{it} = \beta_2 SR_{it} + \beta_3 (SR_{it} \times R_i) + \delta^T X_{it} + \mu_i + \tau_t + \epsilon_{it} \quad (2)$$

Specification 2 uses a continuous ratio and interacts it with a country-level indicator R_{it} that equals 1 when the specific component regularly increases (e.g., due to indexation or stable legislative updating). We rely on a two-way fixed effects panel OLS model, which appropriately controls for unobserved country- and time-specific heterogeneity. While dynamic estimators such as System GMM could, in principle, address potential endogeneity, our dataset does not provide the necessary conditions for their valid application, given the limited time dimension and the high risk of instrument proliferation.

Variable definitions:

- Rev_{it} : government cigarette excise tax revenue in country i in year t
- SR_{it} : specific ratio, i.e., (specific excise tax rate)/(total excise tax rate at WAP)
- D_{it}^{high} : indicator equal 1 if $SR_{it} \geq 0.70$, 0 otherwise
- R_i : country-level dummy equal to 1 where policy frameworks produce regular increases in the specific tax (e.g., indexation), 0 otherwise
- $X_{it} = (Inflation_{it}, IllicitShare_{it})$: vector of controls
- μ_i : country fixed effects, τ_t : year fixed effects, ε_{it} : error term

The first specification captures potential non-linear, threshold effects when the specific component dominates the tax structure ($\geq 70\%$). The second traces the marginal effect of the specific ratio across its full range and tests whether that effect is systematically different in institutional environments with predictable, rule-based adjustments. With country and year fixed effects, identification comes from within-country varia-

tion over time, while time-invariant cross-country differences (including baseline market size) and common shocks are absorbed by μ_i and τ_t , respectively.

5. Empirical Results

This section presents the empirical results on the relation between cigarette excise tax structure and government revenue. The analysis draws on a panel dataset of EU member states, covering the period from 2010 to 2024, with Luxembourg excluded due to its distortionary effect from cross-border purchases. The findings are structured in three parts: first, the average revenue effects associated with a high specific ratio are reported; second, the interaction between countries relying heavily on specific taxes and indexation practices is explored.

5.1. Revenue Effects in High-Specificity Countries

Table 1 reports the basic regression results covering the years 2010 to 2024, with the dependent variable being cigarette excise tax revenues per capita. The results indicate that countries with a high share of specific excise taxes are associated with higher per capita tobacco tax revenues compared to those relying more on ad valorem taxation.

Table 1

OLS Regression Estimates – Revenue Effects in High-Specificity Countries	
	Cigarette Excise Tax Revenue per Capita
High Specific Ratio	10.637* (0.0631)
Inflation	2.2729*** (0.0046)
Share of NDP	-1.5770*** (0.0000)
Country-Fixed Effects	Yes
Year-Fixed Effects	Yes

*This table reports the average slopes and p-values from yearly OLS regressions (Equation 1). Standard errors are heteroskedasticity robust. The table reports the estimates of a High Specific Ratio that is an indicator variable equal to one if the specific ratio is equal or exceeds 70% of the ETY. *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% level.*

Countries with a share of specific excise taxes equal or exceeding 70%, have on average €11 more per capita than countries with a lower specific share. The coefficient estimate on the high-specificity indicator is positive and statistically significant (p-value = 0.0631). To ensure that the observed revenue effects are not confounded by macroeconomic factors or alternative regulatory tools, the model includes two key control variables: inflation and the share of non-duty paid products

(NDP). Inflation shows a positive relation with revenue, as higher consumer prices naturally increase the nominal tax base. By contrast, the negative coefficient on NDP share suggests that a higher share of illicit market activity is associated with lower government revenues. This supports the interpretation that structural tax design, particularly the role of specific taxation plays a distinct and more effective role in explaining differences in per capita revenue outcomes.

Figure 7: Current Tax Revenues and Additional Revenue Potential Per Country if the Share of the Specific Tax in Total Taxation Is Increased to over 70%

Note: Additional revenue potential based on cigarette excise tax revenue. The light blue bar represents current cigarette tax revenues (in million €, for the latest year available) and the dark blue segment shows the additional potential revenue, based on the regression results for the same year.

The regression results (as presented in Table 1) indicates that, on average, countries with a specific tax share above 70% collect €11 more cigarette tax revenue per capita. To calculate the total potential for each country, this per-capita effect was multiplied by the respective national population. This suggests that a higher reliance on the specific tax component is generally associated with higher revenues.

The results suggest particularly high potential in large EU member states such as Italy, Germany, and France. For example, Germany could generate an estimated €888 million in additional revenue, corresponding to 7.5% of current revenues. Across the EU, the potential ranges from 3.8% (Bulgaria) to 14.0% (Hungary), highlighting the significant untapped fiscal capacity that a stronger reliance on the specific tax component could provide. Summing across all countries, the total additional revenue potential for the EU amounts to approximately €4 billion. This estimate is derived by applying the average per-capita effect from the regression to the entire EU population. While actual effects are likely to vary across member states, the aggregated figure provides an indication of the order of magnitude of the untapped fiscal potential at the EU level.

It should be noted, however, that these figures represent average effects. The actual impact may vary by country, being stronger in some cases and weaker in others. Moreover, countries that already apply a specific tax share above 70% such as Sweden and Romania cannot expect further positive effects from increasing this share and therefore show no additional revenue potential. For better visibility, these countries are displayed in bold in the figure.

This difference in revenue highlights that the structure of taxation not only the rate can materially influence fiscal outcomes. This is further illustrated in Figure 7, which compares current tobacco tax revenues with the potential additional revenues that could be generated if all countries increased their specific ratio to above 70%. The chart shows considerable additional revenue potential in several large EU member states, particularly Germany, Italy, and Spain. Countries that already meet the 70% threshold are displayed in bold, highlighting the structural gap between high- and low-specificity systems.

This result highlights the importance of tax composition in determining revenue outcomes. Unlike ad valorem taxes, which are calculated as a percentage of the product's price and are therefore more sensitive to market fluctuations, specific taxes impose a fixed amount per quantity sold, offering greater stability. The observed revenue difference indicates that a higher reliance on specific taxation contributes to more predictable and stronger fiscal performance, particularly by limiting consumer substitution to lower-priced brands and reducing price-based tax erosion over time.

5.2. Conditional Effects: The Role of Indexation

Further analysis shows that the positive effect of a high specific share is not unconditional: it depends critically on whether the specific component is regularly adjusted over time, for example through indexation. The regression results supporting this finding are presented in Table 2. The model includes an interaction term between the specific rate and an indexation indicator, allowing the analysis to distinguish between revenue effects with and without adjustment mechanisms.

OLS Regression Estimates – Conditional Revenue Effects of Indexation	
Cigarette Excise Tax Revenue per Capita	
Specific Ratio	-0.4243** (0.0371)
Specific Ratio * Indexation	0.4806** (0.0562)
Inflation	2.1168*** (0.0088)
NDP share	-1.5177*** (0.0000)
Country-Fixed Effects	Yes
Year-Fixed Effects	Yes

*This table reports the average slopes and p-values from yearly OLS regressions (Equation 2). *, **, *** denote significance at the 10%, 5%, and 1% level. For information on cigarettes excise tax revenues please see Appendix.*

The results suggest that simply increasing the specific share is not sufficient to improve fiscal outcomes unless it is supported by regular adjustments. Without indexation, increasing the specific share is associated with a decline in per capita revenues. In contrast, when specific taxes are indexed, each percentage point increase in the specific share leads to a positive revenue

effect. Unlike the preceding analysis, which used a binary threshold to define high-specificity systems, this specification models the specific share as a continuous variable, allowing for a more granular estimation of marginal effects.

Figure 8: Change in Tax Revenues per Capita by Increasing the Specific Ratio by 1 Percentage Point – With vs. Without Indexation

Figure 8 visualises the estimated impact: in systems without indexation, a one percentage point increase in the specific share results in a decrease of €0.42 per capita, while systems with indexation see an increase of €0.06. This implies a differential effect of €0.48 depending on whether the tax is adjusted regularly. Scaled up, a 10-point structural adjustment could decrease or increase revenues by approximately €4.20 or €0.60, respectively.

This comparison shows that indexation not only preserves the value of the specific tax but is a necessary condition for ensuring its revenue-enhancing potential. The difference between these two scenarios ($\Delta = 0.48$) highlights the importance of systematic indexation for maintaining the effectiveness of specific taxation.

These findings indicate that the benefits of structural reform toward greater specificity are contingent on maintaining the real value of the specific tax over time. Without such adjustments, the nominal value erodes under inflationary pressure, weakening its effectiveness and undermining fiscal performance.

This conditional result adds important nuance to the broader finding: a high specific share leads to improved revenue outcomes only when paired with systematic adjustments to sustain its real burden.

6. Discussion of results

6.1. Why Specific Excise Taxes Outperform

The results presented in the previous section reveal a robust empirical relation: countries with a higher reliance on specific excise taxes experience signifi-

cantly higher per capita tobacco tax revenues, particularly 11€ higher (or 7% higher) on average than countries with a low specific ratio. Summing across all countries, the total additional revenue potential for the EU if their specific ratio increases to over 70% amounts to approximately €4 billion (applying the average per capita effect to the entire EU population). This finding adds robust new evidence to the existing literature, which has long argued that specific taxation provides a more stable and predictable fiscal base. By leveraging a panel dataset covering 27 EU countries over more than a decade, the paper offers a rare empirical confirmation of this hypothesis using fixed-effects regression analysis. The results presented in this paper show that this advantage becomes particularly pronounced when specific tax rates are regularly indexed to account for inflation. As demonstrated, countries with a high specific ratio regularly increasing specific rates collect more revenue, averaging 0.60€ more per capita for every 10 percentage point increase in the specific ratio.

This section unpacks the mechanisms that drive these results, drawing on theoretical and empirical work to interpret the observed outcomes more fully. In doing so, it shows how the evidence provided here both reinforces and qualifies existing claims.

First, specific taxes offer greater predictability in revenue collection. Because they are levied as a fixed amount per quantity (e.g. per 1,000 cigarettes), they are independent on price fluctuations in the market. This has been consistently emphasized in the literature: Keen (1998) and WHO (2010) stress that specific taxation leads to more stable and less manipulable tax bases.

Second, specific taxes reduce price dispersion across brands, which limits consumers' ability to switch to cheaper alternatives in response to tax increases. Chaloupka et al. (2010) demonstrate that ad valorem taxes create wider price gaps across the market, encouraging down-trading and undermining the effective tax burden. This conclusion is echoed in more recent empirical work by Primorac et al. (2024), who find that specific-heavy excise structures are associated with both higher tax yields and greater price uniformity across cigarette brands. Thus, a specific tax compresses price differentials and discourages substitution, preserving revenue and reinforcing public health goals.

Third, specific taxes are generally easier to administer and harder to manipulate. Because they are not linked to the declared value or price of the product, they reduce the opportunities for under-reporting or artificial price setting. This is echoed in World Bank (2023), which highlights the administrative simplicity and enforcement advantages of quantity-based excise systems.

Fourth, regular adjustments or indexation of the specific component are crucial to maintain its real value over time. Without indexation, inflation erodes the purchasing power of the fixed tax, gradually weakening its effectiveness. This is widely recognized in international tax guidance (WHO, 2015; IMF, 2016) and is consistent with the regression findings presented in this paper: only when specific taxes are paired with indexation do countries consistently achieve positive revenue outcomes from structural reform.

Taken together, these empirically grounded mechanisms and established theoretical claims provide a strong economic rationale for why a specific-heavy tax structure, when properly maintained, performs better in fiscal terms than systems that rely more heavily on ad valorem taxation.

6.2. Policy Recommendations

Derived from the empirical findings, highlighting how tax structure and implementation mechanisms can strengthen revenue performance, the following policy measures are recommended:

1. **Adopt a predominantly specific tax structure:** Shifting excise systems toward a higher share of specific taxation can enhance government revenues without the need for raising overall tax levels. Countries with a high specific ratio, collect on average 11€ higher per capita revenue. Beyond stronger revenue performance, specific taxes also deliver more stable fiscal outcomes, as they are less sensitive to price fluctuations, and are more efficient to administer compared to ad valorem systems. This approach also reduces incentives for illicit trade, ensures fiscal predictability, and lowers administrative and enforcement costs. Furthermore, it delivers additional public health benefits, as raising the price of cheap cigarettes reduces their affordability, prevents consumer “downtrading,” and contributes to lower smoking prevalence.

2. **Implement regular indexation of specific levels:** The effectiveness of specific tax systems depends on regular adjustment mechanisms, such as indexation. As presented, countries with higher specific ratio and regularly increasing specific rates average €0.60 more revenue per capita for every 10-percentage point increase in the specific ratio. These mechanisms help maintain the real value of specific taxes over time, enhancing their ability to generate stable revenues.

7. Conclusion and Directions for Future Research

This paper has analysed the impact of cigarette excise tax structure on government revenues across the 27 EU member states over a 15-year period. Using a fixed-effects panel framework, it compared the performance of specific and ad valorem taxation and assessed how design features such as indexation shape fiscal outcomes. The aim was to clarify whether greater reliance on specific excises enhances revenue stability and predictability, while also supporting public health objectives.

The evolution of the literature shows a clear shift from the early theoretical preference for ad valorem taxation (due to its pro-competitive effects) toward the recognition of specific taxation as the more effective and sustainable approach in the EU. Today, with stronger enforcement in place, excise tax policy is guided by three main considerations: fiscal stability, better health outcomes, and closer harmonization across Member States. These goals are most effectively supported by placing greater weight on specific taxation.

The empirical results show that countries with more than 70 percent specific excises collect about 11 euros more per capita in annual revenue. If all EU member states adopted this structure, the EU could gain an

additional 4 billion euros. Moreover, the positive effects are strongest in systems where specific taxes are indexed to inflation, underscoring that design features matter as much as overall levels.

While this paper provides robust evidence on the revenue effects of cigarette excise tax structure in the EU, it deliberately focuses on a specific analytical scope: fiscal outcomes. Several important questions lie beyond this focus and suggest promising avenues for future research.

First, the study does not address the behavioural implications of different tax structures. Future research could combine revenue data with smoking prevalence, consumption, or health indicators to better understand the full impact of tax structure reform.

Second, the treatment of indexation is intentionally simplified to capture the presence or absence of regular adjustment practices. This approach facilitates comparability across countries, but future studies could investigate variation in the strength, design, or automaticity of indexation mechanisms and how this affect revenue performance.

Third, the analysis is limited to the 27 EU member states, which share a relatively harmonized regulatory environment. It remains an open question whether the findings can be generalized to non-EU or lower-income settings with different market structures or institutional constraints. Expanding this line of inquiry to global contexts would be a valuable contribution.

Finally, this study does not explore the political economy of tax structure reform. While the empirical results point to the effectiveness of specific and indexed taxation, understanding when and why governments adopt such structures requires a different methodological approach.

In sum, this paper contributes new empirical insights on an underexplored but highly policy-relevant question. By clarifying the revenue effects of tax structure design, it opens the door to further interdisciplinary research that can assess the trade-offs, feasibility, and long-term outcomes of excise tax reform.

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